

Open Data and AI Safety: Contributions of the Semantic Web to the Evaluation of Large Language Models

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Abstract. The rapid proliferation of large language models has generated increasing urgency for technical governance. Among the tools most commonly used for this purpose are *evals*: datasets with sets of tasks designed to measure specific capabilities or risks of a model. However, their usefulness as a governance tool depends on a condition that is frequently not met: that the tasks actually measure what they claim to measure. This problem, known as lack of construct validity, has been recently documented and is recognized as a priority in the specialized literature. This article proposes that the tools of the semantic web—developed in the context of open data—can contribute to solving it. Semantic web ontologies were designed to avoid indeterminacy and to unambiguously reference entities and concepts. Structured as triples (subject-relation-object), they offer minimum semantic units that can be operationalized as observable indicators of abstract constructs. To test this proposal, an experiment is formulated: building an ontology about the phenomenon of sycophancy and using it to evaluate the content validity of an existing eval. The results of this experiment, along with the ontology itself, will be made openly available to support future research.

Keywords: open data, semantic web, construct validity, evals, large language models.

1 Introduction

The rapid proliferation of large language models has generated increasing urgency for technical governance. Among the tools most commonly used for this purpose are *evals*: sets of tasks designed to measure specific capabilities or risks of a model. However, their usefulness as a governance tool depends on a condition that is frequently not met: that the tasks actually measure what they claim to measure. This problem, known as lack of *construct validity*, has been recently documented and is recognized as a priority in the specialized literature.

This article proposes that the tools of the semantic web—developed in the context of open data—can contribute to solving this problem. To test this proposal, the following experiment is formulated: building an ontology about the phenomenon of *sycophancy* and using it to evaluate the content validity of an existing eval.

2 Open Data and Semantic Determination

In the early 2000s, open data standards were established, largely thanks to the work of Tim Berners-Lee, the creator of the web (Berners-Lee, 2006). In their fullest expression, open data should be 'connected' or 'linked data'. This means that, for example, the metadata or documentation of a dataset should use standardized vocabularies that allow it to be connected or associated with other data or content, making it interoperable.

The W3C progressively defined standards and ensured the infrastructure to make this 'linked data' possible: the semantic web. This involves ontologies and thesauri that can be found on the internet, which assign URIs (identifiers) to entities and concepts and describe or classify them. Semantic web vocabularies typically employ triples—that is, short three-part assertions (subject–relation–object). These are usually represented as two nodes (subject and object) and an arc (the relation connecting them), which is why triples are also called graphs.

Table 1. Example of triples defining 'La Plata' using reusable vocabularies.

Subject	Relation	Object
<i>mtesau:laPlata</i>	<i>rdfs:isType</i>	<i>schema:Place</i>
<i>mtesau:laPlata</i>	<i>schema:SameAs</i>	<i>Wikipedia article</i>

The example illustrates some of the usual syntax in the semantic web. The reuse of vocabularies is common: the concept "Place" and the relation "SameAs" are defined in the *schema* vocabulary and are referenced in the definition of La Plata itself.

The semantic web is thus a compendium of vocabularies that use specific syntax and formats and are open, reusable, and interoperable. They allow entities to be referenced unambiguously; for example, if something is stated to be in 'La Rioja' and the URI <https://datos.gob.es/es/recurso/sector-publico/territorio/Autonomia/La-Rioja> is provided, the reference unambiguously points to La Rioja, Spain, and not La Rioja, Argentina. The semantic web is used to avoid indeterminacy.

3 The Construct Validity Problem

The rapid proliferation, advancement, and ubiquity of large language models has brought with it an urgent need for governance, with corresponding normative and technical measures. In response to this need, non-profit organizations, research centers, and programs have proliferated, formulating proposals and investigating and suggesting lines of research.

Among the most frequently mentioned tools for AI governance are *evals*. These are datasets with a set of tasks representative of a capability or a risk. The performance of the LLM on those tasks is, in theory, indicative of its propensity toward that capability or risk.

Apollo Research, a leading organization in AI Safety research, published in 2024 the article "We Need a Science of Evals" (Hobbhahn, 2024), which argues for the

urgency of improving the methodologies involved in evals so that they can constitute solid evidence on which to base decisions or define lines of action.

In this same piece, the organization defines specific research agendas—for example, it proposes the development of methodologies that provide conceptual clarity about the phenomenon being measured in an eval.

The study described in "Measuring what Matters: Construct Validity in Large Language Models" supports this proposal by Apollo Research. The study analyzed nearly 445 papers on eval experiments and found that, while 78% of them define what they want to measure, 40% do so in ambiguous terms without clear consensus (Bean et al., 2025).

The article argues that this lack of conceptual clarity affects "construct validity"—the quality of an eval to actually be representative of what it intends to measure. More specifically, it affects content validity: the quality of an eval's tasks to reflect in their contents what is intended to be measured. Content validity is one of the components of construct validity, which also requires that tasks be correctly sampled, that there be an appropriate metric, and so on (Bean et al., 2025).

4 **Ontologies for Evaluating Content Validity**

As mentioned above, semantic web ontologies were designed to avoid indeterminacy and to unambiguously reference entities and concepts. They can therefore be a resource for strengthening the conceptual clarity of the phenomena that evals attempt to measure. Their usefulness for this purpose goes beyond a mere emphasis on avoiding vagueness.

On one hand, being open and reusable, ontologies can function as a vehicle for cumulative conceptual definitions: different research groups can adopt, expand, or debate the same ontology, making their differences explicit rather than dissolving them in ambiguous definitions.

On the other hand, by being structured in triples, they provide minimum semantic units that facilitate evaluation. Psychometrics establishes that measuring an abstract construct requires decomposing it into more concrete observable indicators (Bean et al., 2025). Triples fulfill exactly this function: they transform a prose definition into verifiable assertions. Verifying whether a task reflects the assertion "the model modifies its response under user pressure" is a concrete operation; verifying whether it reflects "sycophancy" as a global concept is not, because the concept admits multiple interpretations without any criterion for resolution.

5 **Experiment**

An ontology about the phenomenon of *sycophancy* will be constructed and used to evaluate the content validity of a well-known *eval* designed to measure this problem in models: *sycophancy-eval* (Sharma et al., 2023). The experiment will not seek to prove or contribute anything regarding sycophancy itself, but rather to test a possible methodology for evaluating content validity in *evals*. The phenomenon of sycophancy is used because it is widely described and discussed in the literature and has been

described in slightly divergent ways across different studies, and also because several evals exist specifically designed to measure it.

The following steps will be taken:

Different papers and studies on sycophancy will be surveyed.

An ontology will be created that integrates the various surveyed perspectives on sycophancy and represents them as triples.

A matrix will be created in which each triple from the ontology constitutes a column and each task in the eval constitutes a row. Triples that do not contribute semantic information will be excluded.

An LLM will complete the matrix by assigning 0 to triples not reflected in the task and 1 to those that are. An expert evaluator will review and correct this evaluation, with final authority over each assignment. To mitigate anchoring bias (the tendency to confirm what has already been evaluated rather than question it), the expert will be asked to justify each correction they make.

From the expert-validated matrix, a score will be obtained for each triple, normalized by the number of tasks in the eval. Given the exploratory nature of the experiment, the threshold for acceptable content validity is not set a priori but constitutes one of the results to be determined.

A content validity score for the eval will thus be produced.

6 Limitations and Future Directions

One of the limitations of the proposed experiment is the discretionality over what is added to the ontology. To mitigate this, as much of the relevant literature on sycophancy as possible will be reviewed. An effort will also be made to cover multiple languages, acknowledging the impossibility of addressing more than four or five.

Following the experiment, its results as well as the sycophancy ontology developed will be published openly to make them available for expansion, future experiments, and so forth.

A further goal is to advance the creation of an ontology that defines relations useful for defining phenomena. This would provide an architecture to facilitate and standardize the construction of new ontologies for problems or capabilities to be evaluated.

It would also be interesting to conduct an experiment in which the ontology serves not only as a tool for evaluating the content validity of an existing eval, but also as a resource for generating a new eval with content validity. Increasingly, evals are created with LLMs, meaning that via AI scaffolding, an ontology could be integrated into this generation process.

7 References

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